

DEVELOPMENT OF MOTIVATION FOR EDUCATIONAL AND SCIENTIFIC ACTIVITY OF FUTURE TEACHERS

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Abstract. This article discusses about effective methods and original directions for the development of motivation for educational and scientific activities of future teachers. The article pays special attention to the important tasks of higher pedagogical education and the fact that, in increasing the interest of students in learning, as well as their professional development, the role of teachers is important. At the end of the article, reflections and conclusions about the topic are presented.

Keywords: educational needs, ability, motivation, curricula, learning activities.

РАЗВИТИЕ МОТИВАЦИИ УЧЕБНО-НАУЧНОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ БУДУЩИХ УЧИТЕЛЕЙ

Аннотация. В данной статье речь идет об эффективных методах и оригинальных направлениях развития мотивации учебной и научной деятельности будущих учителей. В статье особое внимание уделяется важным задачам высшего педагогического образования и тому, что в повышении интереса студентов к учебе, а также их профессиональном развитии важна роль преподавателей. В конце статьи представлены размышления и выводы по теме.

Ключевые слова: образовательные потребности, способности, мотивация, учебные планы, учебная деятельность.

INTRODUCTION

The most important tasks of higher pedagogical education in our country are to increase students' interest in learning and provide them with the opportunity to choose an individual path of professional and pedagogical development and self-improvement. Solving these problems requires studying the educational needs of students and identifying the difficulties they face in mastering the theoretical and practical foundations of professional activity.

Upon admission to a university, an applicant from the position of a student (now, at a given moment) moves into the position of a trained person, that is, his activity receives all the features of an adult's activity, which is an important feature of providing a student with motivational impulse. Consequently, the independence of the students, the desire for independence, self-government, the realization of their capabilities, talents and abilities are the main feature of students in universities in modern conditions. In conditions where there is no need for any coercion to learn from the outside, the independence of students as a "motivation for conscious impulse" of actions is the main condition for creating a holistic learning activity. The leading role in the formation of motivational impulse and setting educational goals belongs to the student. Due to the fact that / Since the student's need for knowledge is determined by his need to study certain / specific problems, the practical orientation of educational programs, their comparability / compatibility with the specific goals of each student becomes the basis for organizing the educational process at the university. So, one of the main features of the motivational provision / support of the student's educational activity is the change of his

position / place in the educational process of the university. He moves into the status / position of learning, which accordingly changes the meaning / importance of his work and the role of the teacher [1]

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Another feature of motivational support is the professional orientation of the student's educational activity, which consists in the integration of motives/stimuli/desires associated with educational and professional activities. According to scientists [2], [3], the professional orientation of students is considered to be a typological characteristic of a personality, an expression of its integrity; structure, a set of features that generate meaning/essence, [4]; the core/root of defining professional identity [5]; system of internal conditions (stimuli/motives, norms, values). A high level of professional orientation awakens / stimulates / launches the energy and creative potential of the individual. So, professional orientation and its connection with cognitive independence is one of the most important features of the motivational support of the student's educational activity.

However, it should be noted that the components of motivational provision/support of student learning activities are characterized by certain features. Focusing on the learning situation remains an integral part of student learning. However, in the conditions of a university, in comparison with a school, the content of attention becomes more complicated due to the qualitative requirements for the results of the student's educational activities, associated with a wide coverage of the goals of the educational process, an increase in the number of objects of attention, a variety of types and methods of educational work, and the level of professional training of the future specialist.

P. M. Yakobson distinguishes three different types of learning motivation: firstly, motivation, which can be conditionally called "negative"[6] . Negative motivation to study refers to the student's awareness of certain inconveniences and troubles/difficulties that may arise if he does not study. Such motivation will not lead to successful results if it is not reconstructed.

Secondly, it is the motivation associated with incentives/motives of a positive nature, which are introduced/embedded outside the educational activity itself. At the same time, P.M. Jacobson speaks of two forms of motivation: the first is determined by broad social motives/incentives, and the second is determined by narrow personal stimuli/motives.

Thirdly, it is (intrinsic) motivation included / built into the learning process itself. In this case, the learning process encourages the assimilation and mastery of certain knowledge, skills and abilities.

These forms of motivation for learning never appear in a pure (natural, isolated) form. In fact, learning stimuli/motives are always more complex in nature.

RESEARCH RESULTS

Scientists W. Kennedy and G. Wilcott in their article "Praise and blame as motivating impulses" [7] gave a systematic review (interpretation) of works in which the significance of praise (approval) and censure (reprimand) as incentives / motives in the process of learning. These authors studied works before 1930 and after 1960. These works describe normal/ordinary and retarded children from different special groups, different educational classes. They studied how students performed various tasks: performing arithmetic tasks/exercises and tasks/problems to determine the level of mental development.

The review shows that the results are inconsistent, with some authors stating that praise is a stronger stimulus/push/drive than rebuke, while others have argued the opposite. For example, when dividing the children participating in the test into introverted and extroverted groups, the following conclusion was made: introverts performed tasks at a higher performance level when praised, and extroverts - when blamed. The scientist D. Bruner [8] explores the motivation to study in the following way. The scientist poses practical and theoretical problems that arise in connection with the actual / real, rather long process of the student. This is, first of all, raising the question of the significance of incentives/motives in the nature of cognitive activity in the process of studying/learning and the role of internal satisfaction from learning new things.

Instead of a behaviorist approach to the process of studying / learning, in which studying / learning is considered as a reaction to a certain impact and conditions are determined that make this reaction effective, D. Bruner explores the problem of reward and punishment, and also explores various incentives for the learning process (cognition), that are real/truly appropriate to human. At the same time, the scientist studies the incentives associated with the process of acquiring knowledge: the role of pleasure in mental stress (when doing a lot of mental work) and productive intellectual / thinking activity, the role of curiosity and temper, the experience of “discovering new things”, etc.

When studying the studies of the motivation of educational activity conducted abroad, one cannot fail to mention the work of E. Kron “Motivation for achievement and refusal as the beginning of the definition of epistemic behavior” [9].

The author uses the term "epistemic behavior" as a behavior, an action that involves the expression by an individual of his activity in learning, listening to lectures and raising questions/problems.

Such behavior can be determined by various types of stimuli/motives. These may be incentives/motives external to the immediate goal of acquiring knowledge. An example of such incentives / motives is the desire to get a good mark for one's work, to gain respect.

This type of learning is contrary to the stimulus/motivation that is directed with (through) "intrinsic" stimuli/motives inherent in the educational activity itself. In this regard, the effectiveness of behavior in this study is trying to determine in two experimental situations: when the subjects strive (orient) to the result and when they learn the material on the basis of curiosity.

DISCUSSION

This behavior model made it possible to successfully predict human behavior when choosing a path in risky situations.

The ratio between all these structural components determines the degree of realization of the action/movement.

Different authors indicate different incentives / motives for entering the HII, both in terms of studying this issue, and in connection with the socio-economic and political changes that have occurred in our country in recent years. All this can be noted as sequentially manifesting incentives/motives that do not lose their significance in various situations (forms) of the social system. There are differences in the meaning of motives in women and men scientists. Girls often note the great social significance of the profession, the wide scope of its application, the possibility of working in large cities and research centers, the desire of students

to participate in amateur activities, and the financial security of the profession. Teenage boys, on the other hand, are more likely to say that the chosen profession corresponds to their interests and inclinations. They also add family traditions.

"Professional", "cognitive" and "general social" incentives/motives were more prominent in successful students than in students with average achievements, and were more prominent in students with average achievements compared to those with "utilitarian" incentives/motives. It is noteworthy that the "cognitive" stimulus/motive ranks second among students with high academic performance and third among students with average academic performance.

Interesting information was obtained by the scientist N. P. Fetiskin [10] in the study of the psychological and psychophysiological characteristics of students expelled from the pedagogical institute. When studying the incentives / motives for students to leave the institute, the following data were obtained. Mostly students left the institute due to dissatisfaction / discontent with their future profession (50%); 30% of them said that they were disappointed in the profession, and 20% - that they did not want to continue their studies at the university; and 10% said that they were not satisfied with the situation at the university, and this also indicates the presence of difficulties in adapting to the educational regime and student life. There are more men among those expelled (64%); it is interesting that among the excellent students there are significantly fewer men than women (8% and 92%, respectively).

The implementation of motivational support in unity with mental processes expressed in seven directions, such as intellectual / conscious, scientific and practical, motivational, volitional, existential, sensitive / emotional, self-regulatory, is also a unique (specific) sign of motivational support.

CONCLUSION

In recent years, psychologists and educators have become increasingly aware of the role of positive motivation for knowledge/learning in ensuring the successful acquisition of knowledge and skills. At the same time, it has been established that a high level of positive motivation can play the role of a compensatory (replacing) factor in case of an insufficiently high level of skills; however, this factor does not work in the opposite direction - high abilities do not compensate for the lack of motivation / impulse to study or its low severity, and cannot lead to significant academic success [11]

The scientific researcher A. I. Gebos [12] identified the factors that contribute to the formation of a positive stimulus / motive / reason for learning in students:

- awareness / understanding of the immediate and final goals of training;
- understanding of the theoretical and practical significance of the acquired knowledge;
- emotional / sensitive form of presentation of educational material;
- showing "promising directions" in the development of scientific concepts;
- professional orientation of educational activities;
- selection of tasks/exercises that create problem situations in the structure of learning activities;
- curiosity and the presence of a "positive knowable (cognitive) psychological climate" in the study group.

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